

Principals' Characteristics and Administrative Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Edo State, Nigeria

Ehimwenma Oluwatoyin Louis-Omiyi^{1*}, Philip Igenegbai²

¹Director, Edo State Post Primary Education Board, Benin City, Edo State.

²Department of Educational Management, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria.

* Corresponding Author

Email: philip.igenegbai@uniben.edu

Doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5619801](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5619801)

Abstract

The study assessed the influence of principals' characteristics on their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State. Three research questions were raised to guide the study that adopted the correlational research design. A sample of 60 school principals which represents 10 per cent of the study population was used for the study. The research instrument was a questionnaire titled: 'Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ). The instrument was validated by experts in educational administration and the internal consistency of the instrument was determined and analyzed using the Cronbach alpha Statistic and a coefficient of 0.881 was obtained. The data collected to answer the research question and test the hypotheses formulated for the study were analyzed using mean, t-test statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The findings of the study revealed that the level of principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State is high. Furthermore, there is no significant difference in the administrative effectiveness of male and female principals. However, there is a significant difference in the administrative effectiveness of school principals based on their professional qualifications in public secondary schools in Edo State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that a high level of principals' administrative effectiveness should be sustained through the regular release of subventions and other necessary inputs to the schools.

Keywords: Administrative, characteristics, effectiveness, Influence, principals.

Cite as: Louis-Omiyi, E. O., & Igenegbai, P. (2021). Principals' characteristics and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Administration, Planning & Research*, 13(1), 92-101. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5619801>

Introduction

The principal is the administrative head of secondary schools in Nigeria. These are individuals expected to have proven qualities and knowledge to achieve the objectives of secondary education. They are saddled with the responsibility to undertake all routine activities as school administrators to accomplish educational objectives for posterity. Kelechukwu (2011) stated that within the secondary school system the principal is the Chief Executive Officer, the school administrator, the instructional leader and the personnel manager of both the teachers and students. The principal performs administrative duties such as implementing secondary school

education policies and decisions of the Ministry of Education by controlling the day-to-day administration of the school. In that process, the school principal directs teachers to use their energies for the maximum attainment of the set goals of the institution.

In promoting school administrative effectiveness, the fulcra at the secondary level are the principals. An effective administrative process enhances teaching and learning, thereby bringing about quality education and teachers' job satisfaction. Administrative effectiveness is a function of principals' quality of leadership that motivate and inspire teachers to adapt to the school system. The level at which the principal attain school objectives is determined by his ability to manage his teachers and students. The school principals can review and modify the school programmes to promote good human relations and manage changes in the system as lack of these can create fear, apprehension, and misunderstanding, among other litanies of problems.

Principals' qualifications could be a determinant of their administrative effectiveness. There are varied views as to the benefits or otherwise of principals' higher professional qualifications. In some instances, those with higher qualifications do not get their expected recognition and therefore perform sub-optimally. A study carried out by Eyike (2001) revealed that professionally qualified principals were more effective than those who were not professionally qualified. Principals with degrees in education had more professional output and are effective administratively than those who do not. Babayemi (2006) observed that 'principals should not only be trained in the act of administration but should be well acquainted with the principles that guide and control effective school administrative process'. Kain (2011) in his study on principals' administrative effectiveness of special schools, revealed that principals with post-graduate degrees and professional degrees in general education and diploma in special education are effective principals because they have better administrative training and skills compared to those who do not have.

It was observed that males have dominated administrative positions in the past. However, the gendered structure seems to be strengthened by formal organizations, hence male and female principals now, appear to employ similar administrative skills and styles in the school system, they lead almost alike. Traditionally, it seems as if professional jobs are structured in such a way that the male-dominated administrative positions except in the school system. In performing administrative duties, the male principals seem to be more autocratic, domineering and they tend to create a negative environment in the school system.

According to Maina and Hinjari (2006) observations, the female principals find it difficult to act or administer their schools because they do not want to be seen as masculine or inactive as they play their roles, they struggle to avoid being seen as decisive, soft and not assertive enough. However, the studies carried out by Futrell (2002) and Omoike and Idogho (2008) showed no administrative effectiveness difference between male and female administrators in the school system. This aligns with Barter (2001) studies that male and female principals are rated equally in administrative effectiveness and ability. Ibukun, et al (2011) also showed that there was no administrative effectiveness between male and female principals as perceived by the respondents in Ekiti state. On the contrary, Adigwe (2004) revealed that male

principals tend to do administrative activities better than their female counterparts in the study carried out in Benin City. Therefore, it is expedient to investigate the influence of principals' characteristics on their administrative effectiveness.

Statement of the problem

It is a common sight to find public secondary school students roaming the streets during school hours, attend school when they choose to and sometimes engage in interschool fighting. Similarly, it is alleged that teachers are also involved in truancy unabated, and the school facilities are usually allowed to be misused or rot away, teaching and learning are poorly supervised, among others. These occurrences and allegations involving students and teachers have continued to question the administrative effectiveness of public secondary school principals. The appointment of principals is now opened to every teacher; male and female, and individuals with different levels of academic qualification. The question begging for answer is whether the characteristics of the individuals appointed as principals in public secondary schools are a challenge to their effectiveness?

Research questions

The study was guided by the following questions.

1. *What is the level of principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State?*
2. Is there any difference between principals' gender and their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers?
3. Is there any difference between principals' professional qualification and their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated:

1. There is no significant difference between principals' gender and their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers.
2. There is no significant difference between Principals' professional qualification and their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers.

Methods

The study adopted the correlational research design. The sample size of the study was 60 principals, which represented 10 per cent of the population of 595 principals in public secondary schools in Edo State. The stratified random sampling procedure was adopted for the study. The research instrument used for the collection of data was the Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ). The instrument was validated by experts in educational administration and the internal consistency of the instrument was determined and analysed

using the Cronbach alpha Statistic and a coefficient of 0.881 was obtained. The data collected to answer the research question and test the hypotheses formulated for the study were analyzed using mean, t-test statistics and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Results

Research question 1

What is the level of principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State? To answer research question 1, teachers in the sampled schools were asked to rate their principals' level of effectiveness in performing these administrative functions; students' personnel, staff personnel, instructional programme, physical and financial resource and school/community relation. The responses obtained were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation statistics. The result of the analysis is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Level of Principals' Administrative Effectiveness in Public secondary schools in Edo State as rated by their teachers

Indicators	N	X	\bar{x}	DECISION
Students' personnel	408	1534	3.76	Highly Effective
Staff personnel	408	1330	3.26	Highly Effective
Instructional programme	408	1305	3.20	Highly Effective
Physical and financial resource	408	1170	2.87	Moderately Effective
School community relation	408	1150	2.82	Moderately Effective
Mean	408	1297	3.18	High

Criterion mean = 2.50. (Scale 1.0-2.49, Ineffective; 2.5-3.0; Moderately Effective; 3.1- 4.0 Highly Effective)

The data in Table 1 shows the values of principals' administrative functions as rated by teachers with a grand mean of 3.18. This indicates that principals' level of administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State is high. Specifically, Students' personnel administration had the highest mean of 3.76. This was followed by staff personnel administration with a mean of 3.26 and instructional programme administration of 3.20. The fourth on the rank was physical and financial resource administrations with a mean score of 2.87 and the fifth was school community relation with a mean score of 2.82.

Figure 1, gives a graphic representation to further illustrate teachers' rating of principals' level of effectiveness in the administration of public secondary schools in Edo State among the functions mentioned in Table 1.

Figure 1: Teachers rating of principals’ administrative functions in public secondary schools in Edo State.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between principals’ gender and their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers in public secondary schools in Edo State. To test this hypothesis, a t-test statistic was applied to the respondents' scores to show Principals' gender is not significantly different from their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers. A summary of the analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Principals’ Gender and Administrative Effectiveness as Rated by Teachers in Public Secondary School in Edo State

Gender of principals	N	\bar{x}	SD	Df	t	Sig (2-tailed)	Decision
Male	39	55.64	5.44	406	1.434	.152	Rejected
Female	21	54.87	5.39				

p > 0.05

The data in Table 2 shows a calculated t value of 1.434 and a p-value of .152, testing at an alpha level of .05, the p-value is greater than the alpha, so the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between male and female principals and their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers is accepted. Consequently, there is no significant difference, although the mean of the male principals was slightly higher than that of the female principals. It shows that males are more effective in school administration than females. The implication of this is that both male and female principals in Edo State public secondary schools perform their job in like manner.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between *Principals' professional qualification and their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers*. To test this hypothesis, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistics is applied to the respondents' scores to identify if principals' professional qualification is significantly different from their administrative effectiveness as rated by teachers. A summary of the analysis is presented in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the significant difference between principals' Professional Qualification on their Administrative Effectiveness as rated by their teachers

Professional Qualification	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig(2-tailed)	Decision
Between Groups	884.558	2	442.279	16.139	.000	Accepted
Within Groups	11098.666	405	27.404			
Total	11983.224	407				

p < 0.05

The data in Table 3 shows an F value of 16.139 and a p-value of .000, testing at an alpha level of .05. Since the p-value was less than the alpha level, the null hypothesis which states that teachers rating of principals' professional qualification is not significantly different from their administrative effectiveness was rejected. Consequently, principals' professional qualification is significantly different from their administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State. Post hoc is conducted to identify the difference in their professional qualifications.

Table 4: LSD Post Hoc Multiple Comparisons on Influence of Principals' Administrative Effectiveness

Qualification of Principals (i)	Qualification of Principals (j)	Mean Difference (i-j)	Sig.
B.ED	M.ED	.615	.328
B.ED	PGDE	4.350	.000
M.ED	PGDE	3.735	.000

The data in Table 4 shows a mean difference of principals qualifications; B.Ed against M.Ed as .615 and a p-value of .328, showing no significant difference in principals administrative effectiveness for principals with B.Ed and M.Ed degrees. Table 4 also shows the mean difference between B.Ed and PGDE to be 4.350 and p-value of .000, between M.Ed and

PGDE to be 3.735 and .000, showing a significant difference for comparison between B.Ed and PGDE, and M.Ed and PGDE in favour of B.Ed and M.Ed, meaning principals with B.Ed and M.Ed are more effective in administration than those with PGDE.

Discussion

The finding on question one of this study showed that principals' level of administrative effectiveness in Edo State public secondary schools was high with a grand mean of 3.18. This finding aligned with studies carried out by researchers such as Akomolafe (2012), Kelechukwu (2011) and Oluwadare (2011) on the effectiveness of principals in school administration. This high level of principals' administrative effectiveness in Edo State public secondary schools, could be as a result of the present state government recent pronouncement that principals who have performed administratively well could be appointed as directors and permanent secretary in the ministry.

In its effort in providing the citizens quality education at the secondary school level, the state government is also sanitizing, sensitizing, renovating and building public secondary schools in the state. The schools are regularly inspected and supervised to keep the principals abreast of their administrative functions. These have helped to a great extent in enhancing principals' effective administration of schools. From Table 3, principals' administrative functions on student personnel, staff personnel and instructional programmes were high with mean scores of 3.76, 3.26 and 3.20 respectively. This finding also showed that principals are aware of the importance of teachers and students to the existence, survival and development of the school system, hence their efforts to recognize what motivates and satisfy their teachers are paramount. Principals should also involve teachers in decision making on matters concerning them, the schools and also communicate effectively with them. This assertion was in agreement with Adegbemile (2011) findings in his study on "Principals Competency Needs for Effective School Administration in Nigeria".

The finding revealed the areas where principals' administrative functions were moderately effective such as Physical and Financial resources and School-Community relation with mean scores of 2.87 and 2.82. This was so because principals are not directly in charge of physical and financial resources, such as the purchase of educational materials, equipment and school facilities. Most principals in urban schools do not often interact with communities where their schools are sited compared to those in the rural areas who liaise with community leaders in the renovation of dilapidated classrooms, hiring of ad hoc teachers and supply of essential instructional materials and general development of the schools, where the government is unable to provide everything.

However, there is no significant difference between principals' gender and their administrative effectiveness as rated by their teachers in Edo State public secondary schools. This study negates that of Ibrahim and Al-Taneiji (2012) findings that there was a significant difference in the relationship between principals' gender and their administrative performance.

The difference was in support of the male principals against the females. Male principals are likely to be more daring in performing their functions than their female counterparts. Momoh (2014), Ibikun, Oyewole and Abe (2011) and Omoike and Idogho (2008) findings agree with that of this study. It is important to note here, that gender did not influence the administrative effectiveness of male and female principals' functions in the Edo school system. Therefore, the achievement of effective school administration by principals was not based on gender.

Principals' professional qualification was significantly different from their administrative effectiveness as rated by their teachers in public secondary schools in Edo State. The professional qualification required for principals is a Bachelor degree in Education (B.Ed) or Postgraduate diploma in education (PGDE) for those without a degree in education as stipulated by National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013). Aghenta (1998) affirmed that principals should possess at least a master degree in Educational Administration and Management to occupy the position of a principal. This study is in consonance with Eyike (2001), Babayemi (2006), Kain (2011) and Ifedili and Louis-Omiyi (2015), in their studies on principals' professional qualification and their administrative effectiveness, revealed that principals with professional degrees and postgraduate degrees in education are more effective administrators, because of their additional administrative training and skills. This study showed that principals with Bachelor (B.Ed) degrees and master degrees (M.Ed) in education are more effective administratively than those with postgraduate diplomas (PGDE) in education. Therefore, principals with bachelor degrees and master degrees in education are at an advantage because they are better and effective administrators. Hence, principals with degrees and postgraduate degrees in education should be appointed as principals and not those with a postgraduate diploma in Edo State public secondary schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that the administrative effectiveness of public schools' principals in Edo State is high. Furthermore, the principal's gender has no significant relationship in determining the principal's effectiveness, but the principal's qualification has a significant relationship with their administrative effectiveness.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The high level of principals' administrative effectiveness should be sustained. This can be done through the regular release of subventions for them to maintain and replace damaged school's facilities effectively. They should be encouraged to seek financial assistance from non-governmental organizations to develop the schools and sustain their high administrative effectiveness. Government and stakeholders in secondary education should encourage school/ community relationships so that the community members through the Parents' Teachers' Association (PTA) and Old Students Association can

help to fill in the gap created by government shortfall in the provision of the required human and material resources to sustain principals' high level of effective school administration and teachers job satisfaction.

2. The gender of principals did not significantly influence principals' administrative effectiveness. Therefore, the government should not make gender a basis for the appointment of school principals.
3. This study also showed that principals' professional qualifications had a significant influence on their administrative effectiveness. It is, therefore, recommended that teachers with graduate degrees in education (B.Ed) and postgraduate degrees in educational management (M.Ed) should be appointed as principals in the state.

References

- Adegbemile, O. (2011). Principals' competency needs for effective schools' administration in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 2(4), 22-29.
- Adigwe, O.C. (2004). A comparative analysis of the administrative performance of male and female principals in selected secondary schools in Edo state. (M.Ed. Thesis), University of Benin.
- Aghenta, J. A. (1998). Teacher in recruitment and retention: Issues and problems. *Journal of Nigeria Educational Research Association*, 3(5), 22-29.
- Akomolafe, C.F. (2012). A comparative study of principals' administrative effectiveness public and private secondary schools in Ekiti State. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(5), 39-45.
- Babayemi, A. (2006). Principalship. In J. B. Babalola, A. O. Ayeni, S. O. Adedeji, A. A. Suleman & M. O. Arike (Eds). *Educational management thought and practice*. Ibadan. Codat publication: pp. 242-261.
- Barter, A. L. (2001). *The status of women in school administration*. Educational Horizons Springs. Ww.regent.edu/Accad/.../5-ibukun-oyewole-abe-pp247-247-262-jm.pdf
- Eyike, R.E. (2001). An evaluation of secondary school principals in Edo State. (Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis), University of Benin. Nigeria.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). *National policy on education*. Lagos, Nigeria. Educational Research and Development Council.
- Futrell, M. H. (2002). Pathway to educational leadership, advancing women as principals and superintendents. Retrieved.
- Ibrahim A. S., & Al-Tanaji, S. (2012). Principals' leadership Style, School Performance and Principals' Effectiveness in Dubia Schools. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 2(1) 41-54.
-

- Ibukun, W. O., Oyewole, B. K., & Abe, T. O. (2011). Personality characteristics and principal leadership effectiveness in Ekiti State – Nigeria. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*, 6(2), 247-262.
- Ifedili, C. J., & Louis-Omiyi, E. O. (2015). Demographic variables influencing administrative effectiveness of principals in Edo South Senatorial District. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Management*, 1(1), 20-28.
- Kain, V. K. (2011). High teacher turnover rates are a big problem for America's public schools. www.forbes.com/sites/erikkhain/2011/03/08/high.teacherturnoverratesareabigproblemforAmericanspublicschs. July 13, 2013.
- Kelechukwu, N. (2011) Analysis administrative roles of principals in private secondary schools in Aba education zone of Abie State. *Continental Journal of Education Research*, 4(1), 18-27.
- Maina, B. A., & Hinjari, H. S. (2006). Perceptions of headteachers and teachers on the climate of primary schools in Zaria Local Government Area. *Journal of Education Research and Development*, 1(3), 35-36.
- Momoh, U. (2014). Principals' implementation of quality assurance standards and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo and Delta States. (Unpublished PhD Thesis), University of Benin, Benin City.
- Oluwadare, A. (2011). Principals' competency needs for effective schools' administration in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(1), 43-55.
- Omoike, D., & Idogho, P.O. (2008). Gender disparity in administrative effectiveness of heads of academic departments in Nigeria universities”.
-